

THE ROLE OF SPEECH ETIQUETTE IN JURIDICAL RHETORIC

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7821239>

Abstract

This article focused on the role of juridical rhetoric and used words in it. It goes without saying that rhetoric has been the main sphere for human beings from history till now. The role of juridical rhetoric is important in law.

Keywords: rhetoric, speech, etiquette, jurisprudence;

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada huquqiy ritorikaning o'rni va undagi so'zlardan foydalanilgani haqida so'z bordi. O'z-o'zidan ma'lumki, ritorika tarixdan hozirgacha insoniyat uchun asosiy soha bo'lib kelgan. Huquqiy ritorikaning o'rni qonunda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: ritorika, nutq, odob, huquqshunoslik;

Аннотация

В данной статье речь пойдет о роли юридической риторики и используемых в ней слов. Само собой разумеется, что риторика была главной сферой деятельности человека от истории до наших дней. Важна роль юридической риторики в праве.

Ключевые слова: риторика, речь, этикет, юриспруденция;

Advancements in technology and the quick development of information technology have had such a profound impact on the lives that they have completely changed how people think about politics and society. Therefore, it is crucial to develop argumentative skills and the ability to evaluate other people's arguments because there are fundamental conflicts on important political topics[4]. Whether making an oral or written argument, a lawyer or juror must be straightforward, lucid, and persuasive. This article makes an effort to cover all pertinent facets of rhetoric, the skill of persuasion in writing and speaking. It is believed that agreements or differences on legal, political, and cultural topics always give a writer or speaker the necessary learning push to construct an argument as well as the opportunity to analyze other people's arguments in order to strengthen his own. There is discussed the theory and practice of rhetoric, rhetorical triangle, grammar, logical and ethical components of rhetoric. It also endeavors to explain the means of persuasion and analyses the critical aspects of oratory. The author consciously tries to suggest the readers to go through some outstanding speeches of prominent. The information given here is assisted in analyzing and using rhetorical structure and style, understanding how to convince and identifying when someone is attempting to persuade, and appreciating the value of persuasive communication in r own life. Introduction The use of rhetoric in legal arguments is crucial. It is a very significant aspect of academics. Rhetoric is of utmost importance in all religious traditions, while communicating science to the general public, and when analyzing religious texts. A fine-grained ability to compare various texts, actions, and evidence over time can be developed in

the legal profession, especially by individuals aspiring to become lawyers or judges. Before discussing rhetoric in detail, let's consider what the phrases "this is only rhetoric" and "that is cheap rhetoric" mean[5].

This most likely refers to deceit and empty rhetoric without any real intention. It might be seen as hollowness, empty rhetoric, deceit, and cynicism. The society frequently associates rhetoric with negative ideas. Cheap rhetoric, plain rhetoric, hollow speech, or that's just rhetoric are all examples of rhetoric[4]. For the most part Rhetoric is the study of successful or persuasive speaking or writing, particularly the use of compositional devices like figures of speech. The study of speech and writing as forms of persuasion or communication. The word itself is from the Indo-European language family and is simply translated as "word" or "speech." If someone claims that hyperbole is not utilized or practiced in the financial industry, one would presume such assertion to be accurate, truthful, and open. Hence, it would not be unjust to assert that there is no rhetoric-free zone. The rhetorician, according to Aristotle [4], is someone who can always tell what will persuade. Thus, the definition of rhetoric is the capacity to recognize what could be persuadable in any particular situation. This is not to claim that the rhetorician will always be successful in persuading. Instead, he finds himself in a predicament comparable to that of a doctor: the latter is only able to master his craft if he does not overlook anything that may help his patient, and even then, he may not be able to cure every case[3].

Similar to this, even if the rhetorician fully understands his technique, there is no assurance that he will be able to convince everyone once he learns about the various persuasive techniques. Extraordinary talent and expertise are needed to convince a group of individuals to do what the persuader wants them to. Getting people to listen to , embrace r philosophy, accept , and follow takes a lot of power. And have seen someone convince a sizable number of people to vote a certain way or join a particular faith.

A counter argument and rebuttal is one of the most crucial elements that is frequently included in a rhetorical writing or speech. Debaters are aware of what it entails. A speaker leaves himself open to the possibility that someone else may make a better and more persuasive argument if he is unable to present a convincing counterargument to his own and refute it[2]. If one doesn't thoroughly prepare his speech's arguments and refutations, he will come across as nothing more than a paid consultant eager to say anything for anybody or just follow his own bias while analyzing it. What is needed is morally philosophical rhetoric. It is crucial for the speaker to speak coherently, and for the writer to communicate his point of view effectively, as rhetoric discusses how to speak and write better. Idealistically, the argument should be able to persuade the audience. In addition, when the argument strikes them as reasonable and compelling, the audience is won over. Several Greek and Roman authors wrote rhetorical works and even recorded speeches around Aristotle's Rhetoric[3]. The philosophical key elements of Aristotelian rhetoric were not uncovered until recent decades while constructing a broad theory of persuasion;

Aristotle uses many ideas and justifications that are also covered in his books on logic, ethics, and psychology. One further application of his broad notion of the syllogisms, which also serves as the foundation for dialectic, logic, and his theory of demonstration, is his theory of rhetorical arguments. Aristotle never provides a more insightful analysis of a single emotion than in the Rhetoric, despite the fact that emotions are one of the most important issues in his ethical system. The use of verbal reasoning is essential to rhetoric. As a type of verbal logic,

syllogisms have been examined. In verbal logic[1], are often given a statement and then another statement from which can derive a conclusion. Rhetoric has a natural tendency toward verbal reasoning. In the past, the liberal arts were broken down into three fundamental articles and then further articles. Trivi- is the name for these three fundamental items[1]. These are rhetoric, logic, and grammar. The grammar, including the components of speech, compound and complicated sentences, and object and subject. Better speakers and writers develop when their ability to convince others or present an interpretation increases. The ability to persuade acts as a natural defense against the piercing blades of obstinate mercenaries. The art may be a powerful weapon to convince a tenacious foe from outside the bounds to submit, yield, and give in. Required Rhetoric Every organization depends on effective communication. Every action one does at work is the outcome of communication. How successfully a person communicates with others from other organizations will determine his or her level of professional achievement. Effective communication is necessary to complete tasks, not simply communication itself. By using the right techniques and strategies, the art of persuasion may be learned to a high degree of perfection.

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